

PROBLEMS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LISTENING SKILLS IN ENGLISH LESSONS IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Abstract. *In modern world, foreign language proficiency is essential for intellectual and professional growth. In primary education, learning English enhances children's linguistic abilities, logical thinking, and communicative competence. However, developing listening comprehension skills in young learners presents several challenges, including vocabulary limitations, inattentiveness, methodological shortcomings, and classroom distractions. This article explores these difficulties and examines strategies to improve listening skills, emphasizing effective teaching techniques, interactive exercises, and the integration of audio materials. Addressing these issues is crucial for fostering strong listening comprehension skills and enhancing English language acquisition in primary school pupils.*

Keywords: *listening comprehension, foreign language, primary grades, English lessons, teaching methodology, challenges, vocabulary, fundamental ability, responding, independent learning skills.*

In today's globalized world, knowledge of foreign languages is not only crucial for developing socio-cultural relationships but also serves as a vital factor in an individual's intellectual and professional growth. Particularly in primary grades, learning foreign languages contributes to the formation of children's linguistic abilities, enhances their logical thinking, and improves their communicative competence. According to the Presidential Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021, №5117 titled "On Effective Measures to Promote the Learning of Foreign Languages"[1] various incentives have been introduced, enabling teachers to enhance their professional skills and deliver more effective education to students. This article discusses the existing problems in developing listening skills in English lessons in primary grades.

Before developing English listening skills in elementary school students and identifying the difficulties in this process, analyzing them from a scientific point of view, developing students' English listening skills, finding ways to develop them, and analyzing them from a scientific point of view, we need to study the existing problems in this area. The main goal of developing listening comprehension skills in English lessons is to teach students, starting from elementary school, to engage in oral communication or to understand the meaning of words in English. If we look at the combination of letters in English, we will see that the development of listening skills is a separate issue to be studied.

The main function of listening comprehension is to develop the skill of understanding English dialogues and responding to them. However, students face several difficulties when completing the listening comprehension assignments provided in exercises.

Lack of vocabulary: Difficulties encountered by students include not understanding the translation or meaning of the words spoken during the exercise.

Inattention: Before a listening comprehension exercise, the teacher may not have fully explained the lesson plan or the procedure for doing the exercise. As a result, students may not pay attention to the given tasks or exercises.

Listening comprehension is the first skill and fundamental ability in language learning that language learners need to learn. This is a receptive skill, meaning that language learners learn new words from what they hear or listen to [2]. Therefore, English language textbooks include songs or audio games before the lesson begins, which serves to increase students' interest in the lesson process before it begins. However, songs or games played before the lesson are not considered a source of knowledge, so students should not limit themselves to just these materials. In some cases, teachers also experience difficulties in allocating class time, which reduces their ability to fully cover the topic.

There are also some difficulties in completing tasks to develop listening comprehension skills in elementary school. Such difficulties arise from various reasons. For example, student developmental delays, shortcomings in teaching methodology, and students' various problems in the classroom. The purpose of understanding the difficulties that arise in a student's listening comprehension is to find ways to prevent them [3].

Developing listening skills in students experiencing developmental delays: such as psychologically shy or having hearing impairments, is a crucial task for educators. A lack of support for students or a loss of interest in assigning tasks because they are difficult also leads to falling behind in academic performance.

Shortcomings in teaching methodology: The teacher may not be able to provide sufficient information on listening comprehension skills when working with students. Developing listening comprehension in English requires a number of effective methods. Teaching listening comprehension is an active process of perceiving speech and responding to it. The teacher acts as the lecturer, and the student acts as the listener.

Primary school students' attention is naturally short, which makes it difficult for them to work with listening exercises for a long time. Young students' attention is quickly diverted, especially in the areas of passive listening. Effective listening should be short, interactive, and diverse, which prevents prolongation of the exercises and students' boredom [4].

Therefore, the teacher is required to be familiar with various teaching methods and techniques at the stage of teaching the listening comprehension section in English lessons and to be able to effectively apply them in the lesson process.

Various classroom problems: Noise and other distractions in the classroom can significantly affect students' focus on listening comprehension exercises. A noisy environment makes it difficult for students to listen to and understand the material and complete the task. The lack of computer technology and hearing aids in classrooms creates difficulties during lessons.

Developing listening comprehension skills is one of the main stages in learning all languages, as new information is learned through listening in the process of language learning. In children aged six to ten, the main differences are determined by their cognitive, social, and emotional development. By the time they enter school, children usually don't read or write; due to their limited knowledge, their imaginary and real worlds often align [5].

Taking this into account, starting from the time primary school students enter the 1st grade, English is taught in the following main areas.

The initial topics in the 1st-grade English textbook teach how everyday words are pronounced in English, and they review and reinforce this through audio recordings. This allows students to learn simple sentences like greetings and inquiry. As additional tasks, the names and pronunciation of colors in English will be taught using audio. The color coloring assignment helps develop students' creative abilities [6].

If students have acquired English language concepts and skills in preschool and kindergarten, mastering the topics and performing exercises will be without difficulties. However, when working on assignments like those in textbooks for the first time, several problems arise. For example, difficulties arise when solving simple tasks like naming colors and sequencing numbers.

In the 2nd-grade English language textbook, however, the initial lessons mainly begin with working with letters. That is, the sequential arrangement of alphabet letters is provided, and the pronunciation of the letters is heard in the form of a song. After this, an exercise related to the topic is given [7].

These tasks are primarily designed to develop listening comprehension skills from a basic level, and if the exercises are used effectively, students will gain knowledge of how English letters are pronounced at the beginning, middle, and end of words. What is required of the teacher in all lessons is to organize the lesson process well and to be able to correctly direct it when assigning tasks in groups and individually.

The main task of identifying existing difficulties in developing listening comprehension skills in primary school students during English lessons is to find suitable solutions and help prevent possible student errors. Identifying such difficulties requires patience and diligence from the teacher, necessitating additional lessons and assignments. Identifying such problematic situations requires the development of the educational process and stimulates the development of new teaching methods and methodologies. An additional task for the teacher in the language learning process is to be aware of the students' psychological state and interests. In developing listening comprehension skills, exercises and assignments related to oral communication skills are also important, as students should be able to apply their acquired knowledge in practice. If a student learns only by receiving information, their communication skills will not develop. Students should be able to understand the content of the audio text or the speech of English speakers around it. However, one of the main problems encountered by students is the limited interaction between listening and speaking in English.

Most elementary school students work with English language exercises only in the classroom, which may limit students' independent learning skills, as students may struggle to learn and develop a primary if they lack diverse opportunities and an environment related to the English language.

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